

Effect of drawing process on optical properties of dual-wavelength fiber lasers

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Abstract 35-words

Dual-wavelength fiber lasers are important parts of fiber lasers. We present a study on the effect of the drawing process on the fluorescence lifetime of Yb³⁺ and Er³⁺ ions in dual-wavelength fiber lasers with structured cores.

Keywords: fiber laser, fluorescence lifetimes, dual-wavelength laser operation,

1. INTRODUCTION

Dual-wavelength fiber lasers are crucial in the characterization of photonic components, optical instrumentation, and optical sensing applications. Fibers with a co-doped core of Er³⁺/Yb³⁺ have been traditionally used as fiber lasers or amplifiers. Such fibers can be excited by a pumping source operating at wavelengths of around 980 nm, where Yb³⁺ has its absorption peak. Because Yb³⁺ and Er³⁺ ions are close to each other in the matrix, non-radiative energy transfer between them occurs, resulting in radiative solid-state emissions of Er³⁺ ions. The spatial separation of rare-earth ions (RE) within the fiber laser core can lead to controlled dual-wavelength operation. [1].

The fluorescence lifetime is crucial for assessing the suitability of optical fibers for laser operation. Therefore, knowledge of fluorescence lifetime is essential for numerous theoretical tasks, such as laser performance modeling and calculating energy-transfer coefficients. It was shown that the fluorescence lifetime strongly correlates with laser parameters, such as slope efficiency or laser threshold, where fibers with high fluorescence lifetime typically exhibit enhanced laser properties. The fluorescence lifetime is highly dependent on several factors. Among them, the thermal history of the material is very important [2].

In this contribution, we study the effect of repeated heat treatment on the optical properties of dual-wavelength fiber lasers with structured cores - especially on the fluorescence lifetime for Yb and Er ions and its influence on dual-wavelength operation

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The design of the dual-wavelength preform was based on the modeling presented in [3]. Based on this model, the optimal ratio between Yb-doped and Er-doped areas was 40:60. The preform for the dual-wavelength fiber laser has been assembled using the stack and draw technique. The two types of rods with different RE inside have been employed for assembly. The first type contained Er³⁺ ions, while the second contained Yb³⁺ ions. The preforms with RE were prepared using the MCVD and nanoparticle doping methods. Preforms, Yb-doped and Er-doped, were etched in concentrated HF to reduce the silica cladding

to the proper RE/SiO₂ ratio. Etched preforms were elongated on the drawing tower into 400µm thick elements – this process is considered the first heat treatment of preform. In the next step, seven Yb-doped and twelve Er-doped elements were organized into hexagonal lattices and placed into silica tubes. From such an assembled preform, a fiber with a core diameter of 8 µm, consisting of 19 elements and a 125 µm cladding, was drawn. This corresponds to the second heat treatment of doped elements. The second fiber was prepared by stacking 26 Yb-doped and 65 Er-doped elements into the hexagonal lattice. This stack was then elongated into an approximately 400 µm sub-preform. This is considered to be the second heat treatment of doped elements. The final piece of sub-preform, with 91 elements, was placed inside a silica tube. A fiber with a core dimension of 7.5 µm and silica cladding of 125 µm was drawn, which is considered the third heat treatment of the doped elements.

The lifetimes of both fibers, with two and three heat treatments, were measured according to the scheme shown in Fig. 1, using an EM4 P161-600-976 diode emitting at 976 nm. Hamamatsu G8371-01 InGaAs PIN photodiode with a Thorlabs FEL1400 filter with a cut-on wavelength of 1400 nm for the measurements of Er³⁺ lifetime and Thorlabs PDA36A Si photodiode detector with Thorlabs FEL1000 filter with a cut-on wavelength 1000 nm for the measurements of Yb³⁺ lifetime. The measured fiber segment was approximately 8 cm long. The emission was detected from the side to suppress the influence of amplified spontaneous emission.

Fig 1 – Lifetime measurement setup – Filters were placed in front of the detector. The fiber length is 8 cm for both Yb³⁺ and Er³⁺ ions

3. RESULTS

The measured fluorescence decay curves of the fibers with 19 elements in the core and 91 elements in the core are depicted in Figs. 2. The decay curves of the fibers are single exponential. Fig 2A depicts fluorescence decay for the Er-part of fibers, and Fig 2B depicts decay for the Yb-part of fibers. Corresponding values of decay times for all measured fibers are shown in each Figure.

Fig. 2 Measured decay curves, $\lambda(\text{etc.}) = 978\text{nm}$, A) Er³⁺ ($\approx 1.5 \mu\text{m}$) and B) Yb³⁺ ($\approx 1.1 \mu\text{m}$) right

The fluorescence lifetime of the Er^{3+} ion in the ${}^4\text{I}_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ transition was 10.20 ms for 19 core fiber and 10.16 ms in case 91 core, which is in good agreement with values typically found in erbium-doped silica fibers [4]. The lifetime of Yb^{3+} ions in silica optical fibers is typically between 0.7 – 1 ms [5]. The Yb^{3+} ions exhibited a lifetime of 0.838 ms in the ${}^2\text{F}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^2\text{F}_{7/2}$ in the case of 19-core fiber. However, 91 core fiber exhibited a significantly shorter Yb^{3+} lifetime of 0.756 ms and subsequently failed to achieve a 1 μm laser emission, as shown in Fig.3. Strong laser emission at 1550 nm was achieved for both wavelengths. Therefore, the longer fluorescence lifetime of 0.84 ms suggests a potentially successful dual-wavelength operation. It was shown previously that the fluorescence lifetime of Yb^{3+} may be shortened due to excessive heat treatment, likely due to diffusion and clustering of Yb^{3+} ions, which results in harmful energy-transfer processes between closely coupled ions. [4]. In contrast, the lifetime of Er^{3+} stays nearly unaffected by the same effects.

Fig.3 Spectral output of laser performance of fibers with 19 elements and 91 elements in the core.

4. CONCLUSION

Two types of fibers with exact dimensions but different amounts of elements in the core were drawn using various heat treatments. Measuring their fluorescence lifetimes and laser operation at 1064 nm and 1550nm, it can be concluded that repeated heat treatments have a negative impact on Yb lifetimes and dual-wavelength laser operations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been supported by the Czech Science Foundation, GAP21-45431L, together with Narodowe Centrum Nauki (OPUS LAP 020/39/I/ST7/02143), and co-funded by the European Union and the Czech Republic's state budget under the project LasApp CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004573.

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